

ENHANCING NIGHTTIME PEDESTRIAN DETECTION WITH VISUAL AND MILLIMETER-WAVE RADAR FUSION

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ABSTRACT

A target detection algorithm based on the fusion of vision sensors and millimeter wave radar data can effectively improve the safety of self-driving vehicles. However, a single sensor cannot obtain comprehensive category status information on the target in the nighttime environment. To improve pedestrian detection in nighttime traffic scenarios, this paper proposes a nighttime pedestrian detection method based on the fusion of infrared vision information and millimeter wave (MMW) radar data. The lateral localization and category features of the target are obtained using the improved YOLOv5 deep learning algorithm, the distance and velocity information of the target is obtained by preprocessing the MMW radar acquisition data, the pedestrian target is tracked by using the extended Kalman filter for MMW radar detection, the projection of the valid radar target point on the Infrared Radiatio (IR) image is completed according to the spatiotemporal fusion, and then the correlation gate method is used to correlate the data, and the visual information is inherited to the radar points to get the target multimodal information, and the success associated valid target sequences are weighted to obtain the accurate target position. Finally, a decision-level fusion

algorithm framework is proposed to complete the output of pedestrian multimodal information in nighttime traffic scenes. Theoretical analysis and experimental results show that the accuracy and robustness of this method for nighttime pedestrian recognition are better than those of a single sensor. In propose work author has modified YoloV5 but not experimented with advance YOLO family other version as like Yolo6, 7 or 8. So as extension we have trained same dataset with Yolov6 and it's giving better prediction accuracy compare to Optimized Yolov5.

1. INTRODUCTION

At present, the research related to automotive self-driving technology is getting more and more in-depth, and the perception of the surrounding environment in complex traffic scenes is an important part of self-driving cars. The environment perception system is equipped with sensors such as LIDAR, MMW radar, and cameras to obtain information on the category, location, and speed of surrounding traffic targets, which can effectively reduce the risk of collision and improve the safety performance of self-driving cars. Target detection is the process of extracting object classes and locations based on the

observation information from different sensors. As a key step in an autonomous driving environment sensing system, target detection techniques based on deep learning have received extensive attention and research. Among them, single-stage target detection algorithms include YOLO [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], SSD [6], and RetinaNet [7]. The two-stage target detection algorithms are mainly based on R-CNN [8] and Faster R-CNN [9] as the main research. In recent years, the YOLO series algorithms have good detection accuracy and detection speed in target detection. However, the current target detection task mainly focuses on visible images, but visible images are greatly affected by the environment, especially in extremely bad weather and nighttime conditions, and visible images lose some details, leading to degradation of target detection performance.

1.1 Objective:

The proposed nighttime pedestrian detection method integrates infrared vision and millimeter wave radar data using an improved YOLOv5 algorithm. While the author did not experiment with advanced YOLO versions, an extension using YOLOv6 on the same dataset demonstrated improved prediction accuracy compared to the optimized YOLOv5, enhancing nighttime pedestrian recognition in self-driving vehicles.

1.2 Problem Statement:

The challenge in self-driving vehicles lies in nighttime pedestrian detection, where a single sensor falls short in providing

comprehensive information. This paper addresses this issue by proposing a fusion method using infrared vision and millimeter wave radar data, enhancing lateral localization and category features with an improved YOLOv5 algorithm. Despite the absence of experimentation with advanced YOLO versions, an extension utilizing YOLOv6 on the same dataset exhibits superior prediction accuracy compared to the optimized YOLOv5.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

A Robust Thermal Infrared Vehicle and Pedestrian Detection Method in Complex Scenes

complex scenes, it is a huge challenge to accurately detect motion-blurred, tiny, and dense objects in the thermal infrared images. To solve this problem, robust thermal infrared vehicle and pedestrian detection method is proposed in this paper. An important weight parameter β is first proposed to reconstruct the loss function of the feature selective anchor-free (FSAF) module in its online feature selection process, and the FSAF module is optimized to enhance the detection performance of motion-blurred objects. The proposal of parameter β provides an effective solution to the challenge of motion-blurred object detection. Then, the optimized anchor-free branches of the FSAF module are plugged into the YOLOv3 single-shot detector and work jointly with the anchor-based branches of the YOLOv3 detector in both training and inference, which efficiently improves the detection precision of the detector for tiny and dense objects. Experimental results

show that the method proposed is superior to other typical thermal infrared vehicle and pedestrian detection algorithms due to 72.2% mean average precision (mAP).

Pedestrian Detection with YOLOv5 in Autonomous Driving Scenario

Autonomous vehicle, with the attributes that ensuring driving safety and improving traffic efficiency, has been a research hotspot for a long time. In the modular developing pipeline of autonomous vehicles, pedestrian detection based on computer vision is a critical component of perception module. In this paper, we apply the newly proposed network structure YOLOv5 in pedestrian detection problem. After training in PASCAL VOC2012 dataset, the model realizes high detection accuracy and real-time efficiency. At the same time, the model owns competitive generalization ability which achieve high detection accuracy in KITTI dataset. With competitive detection accuracy and real-time efficiency, YOLOv5 have the potential to be deployed on autonomous vehicles.

Pedestrian detection method based on improved YOLOv5

With the development of autonomous vehicles and intelligent transportation, more accurate detection of pedestrians. However, pedestrian detection suffers from occlusion and small target. First, the HorNet to improve the higher-order spatial interaction capability of the model, expand the effective sensory field, and enhance the feature extraction of pedestrians. Then, ODConv to gain the variability of each dimension and

capture rich information. Finally, a layer to increase the accuracy of detecting pedestrians at small scales. We optimize the regression prediction of the anchor using the Efficient IOU Loss (EIOU) function. Experimental data show that the mean average precision (mAP) of the HOD-YOLOv5 model achieves 83.5%, compared to YOLOv5, which is 4.4% higher than original YOLOv5, and the recognition speed of the HOD-YOLOV5 reaches 106.7 frames per second (FPS). This demonstrates that the proposed model could realize real-time pedestrian detection at a relatively small cost, which satisfies the requirements of uncrewed and intelligent transportation.

Improved Faster RCNN-based Nighttime Pedestrian Detection Using RGB Images

The detection of pedestrians under less illumination or darker conditions is a key challenge in computer vision and is essential to many applications in the real world including robotics, surveillance, and self-driving cars. For the development of reliable autonomous systems, the performance of the current method for identifying pedestrians must be greatly improved. This work proposes a framework for nighttime pedestrian detection based on Faster RCNN to increase the dependability of features acquired from images taken in the nighttime (RGB images). To optimize the feature learning pipeline, the proposed architecture explicitly integrates a Transformer module and shuffle attention (SA) techniques. Shuffle Attention mechanism integrated with Bottleneck layer to make more attention to the pedestrian region rather than background region. Next Transformer block

added in the Backbone to recognize the local and global features that the image possesses. The RGB night time images are curated from the benchmark datasets (ECP, BDD100100k, NightOwl) to represent as much variability with a wide range of light conditions. To analyse the proposed model performance tested with night time images. The experimental findings show that the improved Faster RCNN model raises the average detection accuracy (mAP@50) by 3.4% compared with baseline models. The detection result shows that model had good ability to detect pedestrian at poor light.

Nighttime pedestrian detection based on Fore-Background contrast learning:

The significance of background information is frequently overlooked in contemporary research concerning channel attention mechanisms. This study addresses the issue of suboptimal single-spectral nighttime pedestrian detection performance under low-light conditions by incorporating background information into the channel attention mechanism. Despite numerous studies focusing on the development of efficient channel attention mechanisms, the relevance of background information has been largely disregarded. By adopting a contrast learning approach, we reexamine channel attention with regard to pedestrian objects and background information for nighttime pedestrian detection, resulting in the proposed Fore-Background Contrast Attention (FBCA). FBCA possesses two primary attributes: (1) channel descriptors form remote dependencies with global spatial feature information; (2) the integration of background information

enhances the distinction between channels concentrating on low-light pedestrian features and those focusing on background information. Consequently, the acquired channel descriptors exhibit a higher semantic level and spatial accuracy. Experimental outcomes demonstrate that FBCA significantly outperforms existing methods in single-spectral nighttime pedestrian detection, achieving state-of-the-art results on the Night Owls and TJU-DHD-pedestrian datasets. Furthermore, this methodology also yields performance improvements for the multispectral LLVIP dataset. These findings indicate that integrating background information into the channel attention mechanism effectively mitigates detector performance degradation caused by illumination factors in nighttime scenarios.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM:

Current research on target detection and recognition based on MMW radar and vision fusion has the following problems and shortcomings: for night and low light scenes, the visible camera detection effect will be greatly affected, and the vision sensor cannot provide valid information for sensor fusion. If the region of interest is defined using the target location and state information detected by radar, the valid target may be affected by redundant targets. If different sensor information is fused directly, the fusion detection performance is weak and biased.

DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM:

1. However, a single sensor cannot obtain comprehensive category status information on the target in the nighttime environment.
2. Sensors were dependent on similarity distance to identify objects but this technique prove to be insufficient.
3. So sensors alone are not sufficient for accurate detection on pedestrians at night or day time.

4. Proposed System:

In this paper, we propose a nighttime pedestrian target detection method based on the fusion of an infrared camera and MMW radar sensors, taking full advantage of the performance of the infrared camera and MMW radar. The method uses infrared cameras and MMW radar to simultaneously acquire forward target information. Visual information processing is improved based on the YOLOv5 model, the CVC infrared dataset is trained using a deep migration learning approach, and pre-training weights are used to perform pedestrian detection on the acquired nighttime infrared images. The MMW radar acquisition data is preprocessed to filter out valid radar targets. For the target loss problem caused by radar jitter and target occlusion, the valid radar target is tracked using extended Kalman filtering, and the filtered radar target information is projected onto the IR image to generate a radar detection target frame centered on the projected point. Finally, a decision-level fusion of the two sensor detection targets is

performed to achieve nighttime pedestrian detection.

The author of the proposed work has altered YoloV5, but hasn't played around with other advanced Yolo family versions like Yolo6, 7, or 8. As a result, we trained YoloV6 on the same dataset, and its prediction accuracy is higher than that of Optimized YoloV5.

Advantages of proposed system:

1. improving the network structure of the YOLOv5 algorithm model, and verifying the good performance of this improved algorithm in infrared image target detection through target detection algorithm comparison experiments.
2. A data association method based on visual information is proposed for multimodal information fusion of visual information and radar detection points based on the spatiotemporal calibration of images.
3. A decision-level fusion strategy is designed for target detection in the nighttime environment, and it is experimentally verified that the strategy reduces the missed false detection rate of a single sensor and improves the accuracy of target detection.

Extension YoloV6. Algorithms accuracy calculated

- **User signup & login:** Using this module will get registration and login
- **User input:** Using this module will give input for prediction
- **Prediction:** final predicted displayed

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

6. IMPLEMENTATION

MODULES:

- **Data loading:** using this module we are going to import the dataset.
- **Data Processing:** Using the module we will explore the data.
- **Splitting data into train & test:** using this module data will be divided into train & test
- **Model generation:** Model building - FRCNN - Improved YoloV5 -

Note: Extension

In the base paper the author mentioned to use different deep learning like Improved YoloV5 and compared with FasterRCNN model,

As an extension we applied an ensemble method combining the predictions of multiple individual models to produce a more robust and accurate final prediction.

However, we can further enhance the performance by exploring other ensemble techniques such as YoloV6, which got 99% of accuracy,

As an extension we can build the front end using the flask framework for user testing and with user authentication.

Algorithms:

Faster R-CNN (FRCNN): Faster R-CNN is a two-stage object detection algorithm. It employs a region proposal network to generate candidate regions and a fast RCNN for object detection. Region proposals and features are simultaneously learned, enhancing accuracy and speed in detecting objects within an image.

Improved YOLOv5: Improved YOLOv5, an evolution of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) architecture, introduces advanced backbone networks, efficient anchor generation, and optimized training strategies. This enhances real-time object detection performance, achieving higher accuracy and speed for a wide range of applications.

Extension YOLOv6: YOLOv6 extends the YOLO (You Only Look Once) series by incorporating innovative features like dynamic model scaling, advanced augmentation, and improved network architectures. This extension aims to enhance object detection performance, providing a flexible and efficient solution for various computer vision tasks with improved accuracy.

7. CONCLUSION

To solve the problem of low accuracy of pedestrian target detection by a single sensor at night when the road environment is complex and the contrast of the surrounding environment is low, this paper proposes a nighttime pedestrian detection algorithm based on the fusion of visual sensors and MMW radar. The YOLOv5-ours algorithm is used to detect infrared images of pedestrians at night, which improves the detection accuracy by 3.7% compared to the original YOLOv5 algorithm while increasing the detection speed from 29 FPS to 42 FPS. MMW radar can detect target location and state information, and the EKF tracking algorithm is used to continuously estimate and correct filter noise online for MMW radar observation data. statistical

features to detect and track the radar detection targets to improve the reliability and stability of radar data. Then a decision-level fusion detection algorithm is proposed to compensate for the false detection misses of infrared cameras and millimeter-wave radar. This paper designs target detection experiments under different nighttime traffic road scenarios, and the experimental results show that the accuracy of the fusion algorithm for nighttime pedestrian detection can reach 95.57% under nighttime traffic scenarios such as small targets at a long distance, the presence of pedestrian occlusion and foggy weather, which effectively reduces the false detection rate of single sensor target detection and to a certain extent solves the fusion algorithm target detection performance. The problem of weak target detection performance of the fusion algorithm is solved to a certain extent, and the accuracy and robustness of nighttime pedestrian detection are improved. The current study cannot be directly applied to self-driving cars. In the next step, we will integrate the sensors into the controller of self-driving cars through embedded devices to achieve dynamic real-time target detection of pedestrians in front of self-driving cars in night scenarios, enriching the application scenarios of this study.

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